

Scatter-Plot Assessments of Supply Chain Integration With Operational Performance: In Case of Farmers Members and Coffee Factory PLC in West Guji Zone, Oromia, Ethiopia, Horn Africa

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Abstract – The objectives and the aim of this study that titled the Scatter plot assessments of Supply chain integration practice with on integration Performance in case of Coffee farmers members and Coffee factory PLC box plot indicating the Variables of Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance Positive relationship assumption it indicated that in West Guji zone Oromia, Ethiopia. However, west Guji Zone has consisted of high coffee production environment and potential resources located due to its organic coffee, and an indigenous coffee variety in rural areas it designed with Descriptive Statistics to distribute for 212 respondents, and the questionnaires to be distributed Woredas data can be collected from Primary Cooperatives, Secondary Cooperative Union & Farmer cooperative Union found in two woredas in west Guji zone, Oromia, Ethiopia. Hence, this study basically increased in Supply chain integration measurement indicators like internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance and a strong relationship and a positive direction assumption and it is highly fitted data can be acceptable.

Keywords: Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance and Coffee Factory, Oromia, Ethiopia.

1. INTRODUCTION

Supply chain management it seeks to enhance a competitive operational and Organizational performance by closely integrating the internal and external functions within a company & effectively linking them with company the external operations of industry like suppliers, customers and other cooperatives channel members Mugogo, M. (2020). Achieving Supplier Chain is a complex task (Faculty, 2015) and the benefits of such Supplier Chain integration can be attained through the efficient linkage among various supply chain activities performance in any industry (Wakjira, 2023a) and the linkage and the relationship should have been subject to the effective construction and the utilization of various supply chain practices for integrated supply chain performance of firm industries and a firms that can be pursuing the effective construction of supply chain practices in a company and Supplier Chain practices needs to pay attention to any industry of the business achievements and goals (Fawcett et al, 2008).

As stated by Marcos et al (2010) stated that supply chain integration practices in to through mechanisms may enhance interaction and collaboration in the firm performance it indicated supply chain integration performance (Ashong-lamptey, n.d.2022) says especially in the buyer-supplier interface of Internal integration between purchasing supplier and manufacturing industry groups also played a crucial role and

significant role in supplier collaboration practices in industry at the problem solving process (Case, 2019). Customer integration seemed more important to address supply chain integration problems for Original Equipment Manufacturing (OEM) firms in industry collaboration and satisfy his customer (Ryba et al., 2022). The advancement in technology, and other organizational capacity specifically in information technology performance collaborate with globalization and the complexity of business processes achievement (Wakjira, 2023b) to be shrinking of time horizons are oscillating order-of-magnitude organizational changes in the competitive demands on strategic business management, and on the management of supply chain integration performance (Edossa, 2019).

Accordingly, based on the pre-assessment that conducted west Guji zone members and coffee industry some of the problems can be related to business operational performance (Alemu & Amogne, 2020) it appears, for the reason lack of business alignment among store operation, poor machines equipment and material handling which warehouse and storage aiding machines (Kasisi et al., 2015) says poor business distribution and coffee inventory management integration, problem of keeping steady supply of business pharmaceuticals, role information confusion among some departments and units (Kasisi et al., 2015) says the existence of vital role items of the stock out by problem of demand forecasting and backlog delay. As a result the inconsistency data observed on the operational performance practices of the company (Zai, 2021).

Therefore, this study is to be explored and to be determining the assumptions of supply chain integration with Operational performance in Oromia regional state, West Guji zone Coffee industry PLC, Ethiopia.

2. DETERMINANTS OF SUPPLY CHAIN INTEGRATION PRACTICE

1. Internal Integration

In internal integration in any industries must have willingness to integrate capabilities through data system, and the process internally and externally before it engaged in meaningful external integration in industry. Flynn et al (2010) it explained that internal integration, as a systematic way of creating inter-functional coordination interaction, business collaboration, organizational coordination, data communication and the cooperation's that takes a functional areas together to create a cohesive organizational performance of business industry (Hanif et al., 2020).

The great problem here is that any firms still in practice the traditional information exchanges between the different supplier functions such as telephone, letter & verbal instructions (Das, 2021). Data collection, where house storage and handling mechanisms were highly manual and paper based. However, industry have started to collect the data in the form of soft copy with help of computer orientation and integration practices (Inayat & Jahanzeb Khan, 2021) says in some of the industry which have started also to use information management system process for the same problem through in process (Alemu & Amogne, 2020).

2. Supplier integration

Supplier integration it signifies the systematic process of linkage and interaction between company and suppliers to strengthen the effective flow of resources (Negeri, 2023). The integration of Suppliers leads to significant supplier data improvements in terms of cost and quality while delivering products services to customer and management of suppliers are strategically it is possible to increase the company's competitive business power in terms of supplier flexibility, data reliability, cost and quality maximizations and to improvements the performance if business (Otchere et al, 2013) stated supply chain integration performance it includes different stages involved, directly and indirectly, to satisfy customer requirements.

3. Customer integration

Customer integration perspectives of in different researches that indicated that this dimension is directly and indirectly associated with improved operational performance measurement practices (Devaraj et al, 2007).

However, the other studies that contradicted the customer-facing to operational performance association (Swink et al, 2007) and Customer integration with performance of wholesale companies are positively related (Mago & Mohan, 2021). This means that improving the extent to which the industry ensures customer integration can be a great potential and to improve the industry's firm performance (Teshome, 2018) says the elements of customer integration practices dealt study such as computerization for ease of customer business ordering to establishment of quick ordering system should be ensured for improved operational performance in business industries (Evans, 2013).

4. Information integration

Information integration it refers to the free cost sharing accurately and timely sharing of business information across the members of the supply chain which is a key success factor for an organization (Chege & Otieno, 2020).

According to Lisa Harrington (1999) stated that a Supply chain integration that emphasizes on the flow of business information, and business products along the members of supply chain in an business organization (Amari, 2023) and also encompasses; suppliers, customers services, product producers, and service that providers that integrates together the business acquisition, product purchase, industry manufacture, (Abawa, 2020).

3. CONCEPTUAL INVESTIGATION OF SUPPLY CHAIN INTEGRATION

Source: Developed own (2023)

4. METHODOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION

The entire West Guji Zone in Oromia regional stated it considered as the study population. The reasons it that, Firstly, since the zone has consisted of people with diversified cultures, lifestyles, and economic conditions, there is a high probability that the findings could be at a certain level representative of the situation in other Zone. Secondly, since the west Guji Zone has consisted of high coffee production

environment and potential resources located due to its organic coffee, and an indigenous coffee variety in rural areas this makes to motivate the researcher has a high attention to get findings to search in each zone (Wakjira, 2023d).

There are 10 Woredas in West Guji Zone and regarding the samples, since the number of populations is very large, the researcher categorizes, 10 Woredas into five clusters by using multistage cluster sampling. These are: Bule Hora, Kercha, Hambala Wamana and Birbirsa Kojowa and Abaya Galana Cluster. Among the five clusters, Bule Hora and Kercha clusters will be selected by simple random sampling techniques (Wakjira, 2023c). The researcher selects three sample woredas by using simple random sampling techniques and randomly selected from two selected Woredas data can be collected from Primary Cooperatives, Secondary Cooperative Union & Farmer cooperative Union found in two woredas in west Guji zone, Oromia Ethiopia.

From 452 targets population respondents the researcher 212 respondents was selected based a formula provided by Taro Yamane, (1967) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where, n to be the sample size, N to be the population size, and e has the level of precision. By using this formula at 95% confidence level. and 5% level of precision the sample size obtained as follows:

$$\frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{452}{1 + 452(0.05)^2} = 212$$

Table -3.1: Study area of Sample Size determination

Name of Cooperatives	Total Population	Sample size	Percentage Sample size
Primary Cooperative Union	142	67	31
Secondary Cooperative Union	25	12	9
Farmers of Cooperative Members	285	133	61
Total	452	212	100

Source: Own developed (2023)

5. BOX PLOT ASSESSMENTS

Fig -4.1: Operational Performance
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.2: Internal Integration
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.3: Supplier Integration
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.4: Information Integration
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.5: Customer Integration
Source: Own developed (2023)

Box in box plot indicating the Variables of Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance in West Guji zone Farmers and Coffee Factory in Ethiopia, Oromia is significantly from the rest data set in individual data box plot of non-parametric distributions and display a variation that extending from the box indicating variability of variable in upper and lower layer of data set of Supply chain integration with Operational Performance box plot data assumption is highly fitted in farmer cooperatives and coffee factory in Ethiopia is valid.

6. PARTIAL REGRESSION PLOT

Fig -4.6: Information Integration with operational performance
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.7: Internal Integration with operational performance
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.8: Customer Integration with operational performance
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.9: Supplier Integration with operational performance
Source: Own developed (2023)

Given two categorical variables of Supply chain integration variables like Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance in West Guji zone Farmers and Coffee Factory in Ethiopia, Oromia is there some relationship between the two categorical variables or are the two categorical variables independent and to test Chi-square of independence allows us to test if two categorical variables are independent with dependent variable of Operational Performance are highly related and the direction of predicted measurement variables direction is positive and the assumption measurement variable is also accepted.

Therefore, the test of independence can only show if a relationship exists between two variables, but the test to be show if one variable causes changes in the other variable are shown other variation Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performances specially, Supplier Integration performance are very strong relationship with OP Farmers and Coffee Factory in Ethiopia, Oromia that predicted measurement variables direction is positive and the assumption measurement variable is also accepted (Wakjira, 2023d).

7. SCATTER BOX ASSESSMENTS

Fig -4.10: Sup I, Int I and Op
Source: Own developed (2023)

Fig -4.11: Sup I, Int I and Op
Source: Own developed (2023)

In scattering box plot assumption of Supply chain integration variables of internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance in West Guji zone Farmers and Coffee Factory in Ethiopia, Oromia in classic scattering box that allows it has carefully designed to insure in memorial plaque to create a last platform of data assumption it representing the relationship b/n of Supply chain integration variables like Internal integration with operational performance, Information integration with operational performance, Customer integration with operational performance and Supplier Integration with operational performance in pair of x and y axis is and their relationship is highly strong and box dot direction from x, y axis direction is positively scattered and accepted.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Box in box plot indicating the Variables of Internal integration, Information integration, Customer integration and Supplier Integration with operational performance in West Guji zone Farmers and Coffee Factory in Ethiopia, Oromia is significantly from the rest data set in individual data box plot of non-parametric distributions and display a variation that extending from the box indicating variability of variable in upper and lower layer of data set of Supply chain integration with Operational Performance box plot data assumption is highly fitted in farmer cooperatives and coffee factory in Ethiopia is valid.

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9. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the identified recommendations result and the findings which can be summarized and the conclusion can be drawn and the study could able to forward in the recommendations as a possible to the solution for the identified gaps to be concerned bodies for intervention.

In order to improve to capacitate supplier chain integration performance of the agency that needs to create a long-term strategic supplier relationship for strategic items and so the organization should first classify effectively the pharmaceuticals being procured based on strategic significance improvement, and then it should can be create long run supplier relationship management practices for his practices which have high value, and high importance in the organization with the right suppliers integration performance.

Linking the customer orientation practice in different through the information network with the agency to get feedback from the customer, and creating an access of computerization for customer ordering is a crucial factors while considering the integration of customer.

Currently the internal integration practices can be identified in the study area is good however to made it either best the PLC and industry should have to give a critical emphasis on alignment among any organizational structure through better data integration & creating continuous interdepartmental contact among internal functions and it besides, the organization should have to equipment itself with modern business technologies like manufacturing enterprise resource planning systems, SMEs implementation practices which benefit the company through better integration in whole Ethiopian Context.

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